

DETECTION AND EVALUATION OF FLAWS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING DIGITAL COMPARATIVE HOLOGRAPHY

C. H. Lin, G. G. Genge, L. J. Pearce, and J. C. Suhling
(Department of Mechanical Engineering, Auburn University,
Auburn, AL 36849-5341, USA)

ABSTRACT

Several techniques of nondestructive evaluation (NDE) have been proposed for determining the integrity of components constructed from composite materials. These methods include ultrasonics, radiography, acoustic emission, holography, and infrared thermography. In this research, a new digital comparative holography technique has been developed which is useful for detecting flaws in composites and evaluating their severity. The procedure consists of recording holographic interferograms for flawed and unflawed components which are then "compared" quantitatively to determine the additional specimen displacements due to the presence of the flaw. Digital image processing technology has been employed to improve the resolution and application speed of the comparative holography technique, and reduce the complexity of its optical setup. Also, new procedures have been developed to numerically manipulate the digitized optical data from the flawed and unflawed fringe patterns. These techniques ensure proper magnifications and algebraic signs, and adjust for any mismatch in the magnitude of flawed and unflawed specimen applied loadings. Flaw severity has been evaluated by using a numerical hybrid finite element procedure to calculate the additional stress and strain fields due to the presence of the flaw.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, composite materials have been utilized in structural components for highly critical areas such as aeronautics and weapons systems. Advantages over conventional homogeneous metallic materials include superior stiffness and strength to weight ratios, and the ability to tailor the material to a particular application. However, the application of composite materials presents several challenging problems. Composites are highly susceptible to the introduction of flaws such as bubbles, delamination, porosity, resin-rich areas, and discrete cracking or extensive microcracking of matrix and fibers. These high stress areas are potential failure regions for structural parts under normal end use conditions.

Various techniques of nondestructive evaluation (NDE) are being considered to determine the integrity of components constructed from composite materials. Several methods have been demonstrated to be quite capable of detecting flaws. Although detectable, different types of flaws are often not easily distinguished from one another. Also, no procedure has been advanced to the point where it can generally provide concurrent reliable quantitative information on several critical flaw parameters such as size, shape, orientation, and location. The best approach appears to be a combined application of several of the currently available methods. To be optimally beneficial, nondestructive evaluation of material integrity should be performed on-line at the manufacturing site.

Several optical interferometric techniques are available which have the potential to meet many of these important requirements. They include holographic interferometry, conventional and shearing speckle interferometry, and Electronic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (ESPI). Optical techniques have several advantages over more traditional methods used for nondestructive evaluation of composites. Principally, they are full-field, highly sensitive, and noncontacting. Although relatively new to composites NDE, holographic interferometry has often been used [1-9] to detect and evaluate flaws in composite materials. Under typical conditions, holographic interferometry can be used to generate fringe patterns which may be regarded as contour maps of a particular component of an illuminated object's surface displacement. Successful application of holography to flaw characterization relies on the fact that the presence of a flaw will alter the stresses, strains, and displacements in a loaded specimen near the locality of a flaw. These alterations are manifested in unexpected anomalies (abrupt changes) in the obtained holographic fringe patterns. For a flawed specimen under a given loading, the fringe patterns indicate a summation of the typical displacements for an unflawed specimen (subjected to that same loading) with the additional displacements due to the flaw. Therefore, understanding of the experimental results is not always straightforward.

In the case of delaminations, studies [3-4,9] have shown that the delamination locations are easily identified by the appearance of sudden dense bull's-eye fringe concentrations in an otherwise slowly varying holographic fringe pattern. Other flaws have a more subtle influence on the experimental measurements so "comparative" holography techniques [5-8] are often used. Generally, these methods consist of revealing irregularities by comparing in some manner the optical interference fringe patterns generated for suspected flawed components

to those of a nominally identical unflawed or "perfect" reference specimen subjected to the same state of loading conditions. The comparison has been done in a purely qualitative manner using human and/or computer fringe density decision processes [5]. However, several of the proposed comparative holography techniques [6-8] lead directly to a set of displacement difference fringes which show quantitatively the additional displacements due to the presence of a flaw. These methods involve complicated optical configurations which are difficult to implement quickly or in an automated environment. Also, they produce "holographic-moire" fringes which are of relatively poor quality. Such fringes can be difficult to locate precisely and can be subject to a variety of experimental errors. In this work, a new digital comparative holography technique is proposed which has the potential to alleviate several of the shortcomings of earlier methods.

HOLOGRAPHIC INTERFEROMETRY

Holography is a technique where the image of a three-dimensional object can be stored on and then later retrieved from a two-dimensional photographic recording material. Unlike a conventional photograph, a hologram preserves the scene's true three-dimensional nature. A typical setup for constructing a hologram is illustrated in Figure 1. During a holographic exposure, a coherent beam of laser light is split into two components referred to as the object and reference beams which are expanded into spherical wavefronts. The object beam illuminates the specimen of interest and scatters diffusely back to the holographic film plate, while the reference beam proceeds directly to the film. At the hologram, the two wavefronts superimpose and interfere. After photographically processing the film plate, a complicated intensity distribution (diffraction grating) resulting from the interference of the two wavefronts is found to exist. A three-dimensional virtual image of the original object can be viewed through the developed hologram by illuminating it with the reference beam only.

Figure 1

Figure 2

In holographic interferometry, two slightly different scattered object wavefronts are made to interfere revealing an image containing dark interference bands superimposed on the object (a so-called fringe pattern). Holographic interferometric fringes can be obtained by real-time or double exposure methods. For displacement measurements, one object wavefront is taken from an unloaded specimen and the other is taken from the same specimen with applied loading (and thus slightly distorted). In this case, it can be shown that the fringe patterns are contour maps of surface displacement. The deformation direction to which the holographic interferometry measurement is sensitive is dictated by the geometry of the optical setup. Referring to Figure 2, the observed intensity distribution of the fringe pattern is governed by [9]

$$I = I_0 \cos^2(\Delta/2) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\Delta = (2\pi/\lambda) [(\vec{e}_2 - \vec{e}_1) \cdot \vec{u}] \quad (2)$$

In most applications (including this work), holographic interferometry is utilized to measure the portion of an object's displacement vector which is normal to the illuminated surface. The optical configuration is chosen so that $\vec{e}_2 = -\vec{e}_1 = \vec{k}$, and eq. (1) reduces to

$$I = I_0 \cos^2(2\pi u_z/\lambda) \quad (3)$$

where u_z is the z-component of the displacement vector (normal to the surface). The center of the bright fringes (maximum intensity) occur when $I = I_0$ or

$$u_z = N (\lambda/2) \quad N = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (4)$$

where N is the integral fringe order. Equation (2) is often used for points not at the center of a bright fringe. The fringe order N is then not restricted to integer values.

In general, it is impossible to determine the direction and magnitude of the surface displacements from a

holographic fringe pattern alone since the fringe pattern contains light intensity information only. From eq. (3) it can be seen that several possible displacement values u_z will give the same intensity which means for a given intensity value, the magnitude of the displacement is ambiguous. If considering the centers of the bright fringes only, this corresponds to not being able to identify the fringe order N . Therefore, intuitive knowledge of expected structural behavior and/or known displacement boundary conditions are often used when analyzing fringe patterns. However, such methods are not always applicable.

A more foolproof approach to fringe pattern analysis is based upon the use of carrier fringes [10-11]. The method consists of introducing displacements due to a known out-of-plane rigid body rotation in addition to the loading induced deformations. This causes a linear displacement field which appears as a set of parallel fringes to be added to the fringes due to the applied loading. If the slope of the linear field is large (the carrier fringes dominate), then the total displacements (rotation plus loading) will increase/decrease monotonically along lines perpendicular to the carrier fringes. Equation (3) or (4) can then be used in a quantitative manner along lines perpendicular to the carrier fringes to yield the displacements to within a fixed constant. The constant can be determined by known boundary conditions on the total displacements or by fringe following when using real-time holographic interferometry. The known linear distribution is then subtracted from the measured total displacements to yield the desired displacements due to the applied loading.

DIGITALLY DETERMINED DISPLACEMENT FIELDS

Modern digital imaging equipment is well suited to aid in automatic computerized holographic fringe pattern analysis. In an image digitization system, a composite video signal from a camera is digitized by a frame grabber. The frame grabber subdivides the image into an array of rectangular picture elements (pixels) and assigns to each element a digital intensity value (one of 256 gray levels for eight bit resolution). These values are quickly stored in the frame grabber's memory which can be synonymous to or translated to the host computer's memory.

In practice, the intensity distribution over a holographic fringe pattern can be so partitioned and digitized. If a suitable set of carrier fringes has been introduced, the displacements will vary monotonically along lines perpendicular to the carrier fringes. The orientation of the rectangular pixels of the image digitizer should then be chosen so that the sides of the pixels are parallel to and perpendicular to the carrier fringes. This will ensure that the total displacements will be monotone along lines of pixels. The pixel intensity values can then be translated unambiguously into a discrete set of pixel displacement values using eq. (3). The known linear distribution which causes the carrier fringes can be subtracted to generate pixel displacement values due only to the applied loading. Finally, a curve fitting routine can be applied to the discrete set of pixel displacement values to yield a continuously interpolated displacement field for the entire portion of the structure which has been digitized.

All of the above operations can be implemented on a computer since the intensity values are stored in memory. Matthys, et al [10] and Hung [11] have previously demonstrated such computer-aided processing of holographic fringe patterns. In practice, optical noise such as laser speckle exists over the intensity distribution of a fringe pattern so that filtering/smoothing procedures must be applied to the digitized intensity data along lines of pixels before using eqs. (3) or (4).

DIGITAL COMPARATIVE HOLOGRAPHY

A new automated method for analyzing flaws in composite materials using the principles of comparative holography has been implemented with the aid of computerized holographic fringe pattern analysis. In its most simple form, the procedure consists of recording holographic interferograms of nominally identical flawed and unflawed components subjected to the same loading and boundary conditions. Carrier fringes are introduced into both fringe patterns so that they are conveniently analyzed with the aid of an image digitizer and computer to determine numerically the out-of-plane displacement fields for each specimen. The two displacement fields can be subtracted to determine the net additional displacement distribution due to the presence of the flaw. This distribution can then be visualized as a computer generated surface plot or contour map to aid in flaw detection and characterization, as well as evaluation of flaw severity.

In an idealized inspection system, the unflawed or "perfect" reference specimen need be analyzed only once and its displacement distribution stored in computer memory for future reference. Specimens with suspected flaws could then be processed in assembly line fashion. Utilization of a thermoplastic holographic recording system would allow for quick formation of fringe patterns using real-time holographic interferometry. It is estimated that the whole process from inserting the evaluation specimen to display of the additional displacements relative to the reference specimen can be performed within a minute provided that a suitably powerful host computer system is utilized.

The procedure is not without possible experimental errors. As discussed previously, noise in the intensity distributions of the holographic interferograms will necessitate smoothing and filtering of the digitized intensity data before displacements can be calculated. The carrier fringe distribution (magnitude of the rigid body rotation) must also be known exactly. Finally, the magnitudes of the applied loadings for flawed and unflawed specimens must be identical. If not, the calculated displacement difference distribution would be a result not only of the flaw, but also due to load magnification differences. Such errors would hamper the utility of the method.

Precise determination of the rotation used to generate the carrier fringes can be accomplished using real-time holographic interferometry and an additional image digitization. A single exposure hologram is made for the unloaded specimen (flawed or reference) and developed. Then a rotation is applied to create carrier fringes

in a real-time holographic interferometry configuration. This fringe pattern is digitized and computer processed to yield the rotational displacements at discrete pixel locations. These data are fit with a two-dimensional linear regression analysis to precisely determine the slope of the rigid body rotation. After processing on the carrier pattern is completed, the specimen is loaded to create a fringe pattern due to the sum of the rotational displacements and the deformations due to the loading. After processing this fringe pattern to determine the total displacement distribution, the known carrier fringe displacements are subtracted to yield the displacements due to the loading only.

Elimination of load mismatch effects can be treated as follows. The displacement distributions of flawed and unflawed components due to loading alone are first calculated as discussed above. If the flawed component is assumed to behave as a linear elastic material (even near the flaw), then the relationship between the displacements at a fixed point in the flawed specimen at the different loadings is

$$u_f(P_r) = (P_r/P_f) u_f(P_f) \quad (5)$$

where P_f is the loading on the flawed component, P_r is the loading on the unflawed reference component, $u_f(P_f)$ is the measured displacement of the flawed component at load P_f , and $u_f(P_r)$ is the unknown displacement of the flawed component at load P_r . If the loading ratio is known, the displacement difference normalized to be at the reference loading would be

$$[u_f(P_r) - u_r(P_r)] = (P_r/P_f) u_f(P_f) - u_r(P_r) \quad (6)$$

where the quantities on the right hand side of the equation are all known.

In many cases, the loading ratio can be accurately measured using high quality load transducers. An alternative measure would be to calculate an approximate loading ratio from the raw displacement data measured for the flawed and unflawed specimens. By rearranging eq. (6), the known ratio of the measured flawed and unflawed displacements is

$$[u_f(P_f) / u_r(P_r)] = (P_f/P_r) [u_f(P_r) / u_r(P_r)] \quad (7)$$

Away from the flaw, its effect on the displacement field is usually negligible so that the flawed and unflawed specimen displacements at load P_r are approximately equal. In that case, eq. (7) may be approximated as

$$[u_f(P_f) / u_r(P_r)] = (P_f/P_r) \quad (8)$$

and the inverse loading ratio can be calculated. A selective algorithm has been developed which calculates the average value of the ratio $[u_f(P_f) / u_r(P_r)]$ over all pixel locations not near the flaw. This average value is then used to determine the inverse loading ratio using eq. (8). The process of selecting points to be included in the average is based on a slope criterion which examines the finite difference derivative values of the uncorrected displacement difference $[u_f(P_f) - u_r(P_r)]$. If a derivative is too large (when compared to a specified tolerance level), that point is rejected as being too influenced by the flaw and not included in the average.

EXAMPLE APPLICATION

The proposed digital comparative holography technique was evaluated by considering both high quality, and intentionally flawed unidirectional composite material laminates. The flawed laminates included resin rich areas which had greatly reduced stiffness and strength. The laminate material was unidirectional glass-epoxy. In the configuration considered, square plates were clamped on their boundaries and subjected to uniform normal pressure. Figure 3 illustrates the holographic fringe patterns for unflawed and flawed components under similar magnitude of loading. A fringe pattern anomaly is clearly visible below the center of the flawed laminate. These fringe patterns are actually not utilized in the digital comparative holography procedure proposed in this paper and are presented here for visualization purpose only.

To implement the comparative holography procedure, four different holographic fringe patterns are created using real time holographic interferometry and digitized. These fringe patterns consist of the unflawed (reference) specimen rigid body rotation carrier fringes, the flawed specimen rigid body rotation carrier fringes, the unflawed specimen subjected to rotation and loading, and the flawed specimen subjected to rotation and loading as shown in Figures 4a-4d, respectively. The displacement distributions in the unflawed and flawed specimens due to the loading alone are then calculated using the computerized procedure described previously. These discrete pixel displacement values may be curve fit and interpolated to obtain a magnified surface plot of the out-of-plane displacement distributions as shown in Figure 5. It should be noted that the displacements are known much more precisely than indicated since the mesh of the digitizer pixels (512 x 512) is much finer than the mesh of the surface plot (40 x 40).

The ratio of flawed to unflawed specimen loading was calculated as discussed earlier, and then the corrected displacement difference distribution was calculated using eq. (6). The additional displacements due to the flaw may be visualized as indicated in Figures 6 and 7. Figure 6 contains a magnified surface plot of the displacement differences while Figure 7 is a numerically generated image of an equivalent holographic fringe pattern (displacement contour map) calculated from the displacement difference distribution. Both clearly show the location of the flaw.

Unflawed

Flawed

Figure 3

(a) Unflawed Carrier Fringes

(b) Flawed Carrier Fringes

(c) Unflawed - Carrier and Loading

(d) Flawed - Carrier and Loading

Figure 4

Unflawed

Flawed

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

HYBRID STRESS ANALYSIS

A potential method to estimate flaw severity is to consider a flawed specimen under in-service loading conditions and to then calculate the additional stresses and strains which exist due to the presence of the flaw. In this work, a hybrid stress analysis [12] procedure was implemented. The experimentally determined additional displacements due to the flaw were used as input boundary and constraint conditions to a numerical plate solution using the finite element method. For example, Figure 8 shows the calculated additional stress distribution for $\sigma_x = \sigma_1$ in the flawed glass-epoxy laminate considered previously. A 40 x 40 mesh of plate elements was used, and the solution was constrained to the displacement differences as shown in Figure 6. Note that the additional stresses are essentially zero away from the flaw.

These hybrid stress analysis results can only be considered as estimates since they are based on the normal material properties of the unflawed plate (and linear elastic behavior), and the analysis assumes that the flawed specimen behaves as a plate (plane sections remain plane) even in the region of the flaw.

Figure 8

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A new digital comparative holography technique for detection and evaluation of flaws in composite materials has been presented and demonstrated. The method is easily automated using real-time holographic interferometry via a thermoplastic recording system and computer processing of digitized image intensities. Additional stress fields due to flaws have been estimated using a numerical hybrid stress analysis procedure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the U.S. Army Research Office (Contract No. DAAL 03-86-G-0211). Mr. Y. P. Wu provided valuable photographic assistance in this study.

REFERENCES

1. Maddux, G. E. and Sendekyj, G. P., "Holographic Techniques for Defect Detection in Composite Materials," in *Nondestructive Evaluation and Flaw Criticality for Composite Materials*, ASTM STP 696, Edited by R. B. Pipes, pp. 26-44, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1979.
2. Sendekyj, G. P., Maddux, G. E., and Tracy, N. A., "Comparison of Holographic, Radiographic and Ultrasonic Techniques for Damage Detection in Composite Materials," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM II)*, Toronto, Canada, April 16-20, 1978, pp. 1037-1056, 1978.
3. Erf, R. K., *Holographic Nondestructive Testing*, Academic Press, 1974.
4. Grunewald, K., Fritzsich, W., Harnier, A. and Roth, E., "Nondestructive Testing of Plastics by Means of Holographic Interferometry," *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 15(1), pp. 16-28, 1975.
5. Tichenor, D. A. and Madsen, V. P., "Computer Analysis of Holographic Interferograms for Nondestructive Testing," in *Image Understanding Systems and Industrial Applications*, SPIE Vol. 155, pp. 222-227, 1978.
6. Youren, X., Vest, C. M. and Delp, E. J., "Digital and Optical Moire Detection of Flaws Applied to Holographic Nondestructive Testing," *Optics Letters*, Vol. 8(8), pp. 452-454, 1983.
7. Neumann, D. B., "Comparative Holography: A Technique for Eliminating Background Fringes in Holographic Interferometry," *Optical Engineering*, Vol. 24(4), pp. 625-627, 1985.
8. Rastogi, P. K., "Comparative Holographic Interferometry: A Nondestructive Inspection System for Detection of Flaws," *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol 25(4), pp. 325-337, 1985.
9. Vest, C. M., *Holographic Interferometry*, John Wiley and Sons, 1979.
10. Matthys, D. A., Gilbert, J. A. and Dudderar, T. D., "Automated Analysis of Holographic Interferograms for Determination of Surface Displacement," *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol 28(1), pp. 86-91, 1988.
11. Hung, Y. Y., "A PC-Based Image Processing System for Automatic Deduction of Holographically Recorded Displacement," in the *Proceedings of the VI International Congress on Experimental Mechanics*, Portland, OR, June 6-10, 1988, pp. 676-682, 1988.
12. Kobayashi, A. S., "Hybrid Experimental-Numerical Stress Analysis," *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol. 23(3), pp. 338-347, 1983.